

MAGNESIUM PARTICLE COMPOSITES

J. Schröder, K. U. Kainer and B. L. Mordike
Institut für Werkstoffkunde und Werkstofftechnik, TU Clausthal,
Agricolastraße 6, D-3392 Clausthal-Zellerfeld

Magnesium alloys have assumed increased importance as construction material where weight and hence energy must be saved. The disadvantages of low strength, low elastic modulus, poor fatigue resistance and insufficient high temperature strength prevent their use in applications where stringent requirements must be met. Particle reinforcement can remove many of the disadvantages and enable alloys to meet many demands in aircraft, space and automobile applications. Additions of SiC, TiC, Al₂O₃ etc. improve elastic and mechanical properties at room and elevated temperatures. There is also an improvement in wear resistance and a beneficial reduction in thermal expansion. Suitable dispersing methods are available to ensure optimum distribution of particles. In this work the mechanical properties, the microstructure and technological properties of particle reinforced magnesium alloys are presented and discussed. The influence of particle content, type of particle and distribution on the properties is discussed.